

Milestone 4: Sustainability Report Work Plan

1. Introduction

This milestone paper presents a plan of action to allow the production of a sustainability report for deliverable D1.5. The paper outlines the data collection to allow appropriate assessment of the sustainability of the services provided by West-Life and actions for the provision of the services required by the structural biology community beyond the lifetime of the project. In section 2, sustainability is discussed with particular reference to sustainability aims for e-Infrastructures. In section 3, the plans for data collection and data sources available for sustainability assessment are outlined. Section 4 explains how the data collected will allow the assessment of how each West-Life service, and ultimately inform decisions on sustainability actions. Finally, the work plan towards the project-end deliverable D1.5 Sustainability Report is detailed in section 5.

2. Sustainability Aims and Recommendations

In the second volume of the ESFRI Scripta: Long Term Sustainability of Research Infrastructures, the ESFRI LTS working group set out 7 main recommendations [1]. These are:

1. Establish and maintain excellence
2. Ensure that RIs have the right people in the right place at the right time
3. Integrate a vision for convergent operation of RIs and e-Infrastructures
4. Fully exploit the potential of RIs as innovation hubs
5. Determine the economic and wider societal value of RIs
6. Establish effective governance and sustainable long-term funding for RIs at every stage in their lifecycle
7. Foster broader coordination at National and European Levels

The recommendations are tailored towards RIs, however, there is overlap between sustainability considerations required on an RI level and on a service level. In particular, recommendation 1 places focus on excellence, and in particular maintenance of excellence. This is directly applicable to all of the services provided by West-Life and means to establish the excellence of the services provided, and to ensure that such excellence is maintained in the future, are crucial for their sustainability. Maintenance of excellence requires planned future developments to ensure that the service provision remains at the cutting edge of research services. Recommendation 4 also highlights innovation as a key area for sustainability. It is not possible to maintain excellence without innovation. Recommendation 5 underlines the importance of the wider socio-economic impact. Services with a large impact to society as a whole show a value which deserves to be maintained therefore encouraging external investment and support.

Voss et. al. discuss the sustainability of e-Infrastructures, and outline sustainability aims, risks and approaches to mitigate these risks [2]. West-Life, though a Horizon 2020 funded project, is

most similar to an e-Infrastructure, an infrastructure of computational tools and services, and therefore the aims of Voss et. al. are applicable to West-Life. The aims that they present are:

1. Dependable services and long-term availability of infrastructure
2. Independence of infrastructure from single providers or funding sources
3. Long-term added value through an established base that new activities can build on
4. Realisation of the benefits of investments made
5. Ability to effectively plan investments and activities
6. A growing body of knowledge shared throughout the community
7. Technical evolution that does not lead to legacy issues
8. Embedding of e-Infrastructures in everyday research practice
9. Users' needs are met and the costs of uptake are low enough
10. e-Science 'sells' and an increasing number of users are getting engaged

To determine the appropriate sustainability actions going forward, we will first establish how well these aims are currently being met by West-Life services using the data collection sources outlined. For services already meeting the sustainability aims, it should be trivial to absorb these services into a sustainability plan. For those services which fail to meet key sustainability aims, further work will be required and actions must be taken to allow such services to achieve the sustainability aims, or to be decommissioned.

West-Life as a whole will need to either establish itself as an organisation in its own right following the project end, or be decommissioned. Should West-Life continue it would need to establish suitable governance, legal framework, and funding model.

Ultimately each individual West-Life service will either:

- a. Be adopted by a (new or existing) organisation (e.g. Instruct-ERIC) or funded project which would then absorb the costs for maintaining/developing the service.
- b. Continue in its present form. This requires evidence that the service has sufficient funding/infrastructure in place.
- c. Be decommissioned.

3. Data Collection: Outline of data sources

Data source 1: West-Life Sustainability Questionnaire

The West-Life Sustainability Questionnaire due to be distributed in May 2018 aims to collect data for each West-Life service in 5 categories: About service, User registration, Service use, Service support, Commitment to service, Impact of service, Sustainability of service. A draft questionnaire has been circulated to West-Life partners for feedback which has then been used to compile the final version of the questionnaire. The full list of questions are provided in appendix A.

Data source 2: West-Life Deliverable D5.7 [3]: Report on access and usage statistics of the various services

This deliverable provides usage statistics KPI for the usages of West-Life Services, and additional information for each service such as information on whether the service is

Grid-enabled, whether the service is Cloud-enabled, how long the service has been operational, url for the service, and key publications.

Data source 3: West-Life Work Package 5: Additional data collection

The additional data collection by work package 5 focuses on the impact of services, user satisfaction, and new developments. Recently a user satisfaction plugin has been developed to collect user feedback using a simple 'expression-based' rating as shown in figure 1 (<https://h2020-westlife-eu.gitbook.io/satisfaction-plugin>).

Figure 1: User satisfaction plugin as viewed by the user. Implemented on some West-Life services to collect feedback.

Full details of the information requested are provided in Appendix B.

Data source 4: West-Life Work Package 2 Deliverable D2.5: Engagement report

For the preparation of D2.5, data on West-Life outreach activities is being compiled. This data will help inform the impact of West-Life and its services. Full details of the information requested are provided in Appendix C.

4. How the sustainability aims will be assessed through the planned data collection

The aims presented by Voss et. al. [2] can each be assessed by one or more of the data sources in section 3. In this section we explain how data collected feeds into the assessment of each sustainability aim in [2].

1. Dependable services and long-term availability of infrastructure

Data sources:

- Data source 1: Questions 5, 6, 12, 14, 15, 22, 23

Explanation:

We collect data on the current service provision and the modalities through which the service can be accessed currently in q5 and q6. These data help to assess the availability of the service. Q12 collects information about support provided for the service, which is necessary for the service and also contributes to its long-term availability. Q14 provides information about how long the service has been operational - a proven track record for past availability can help inform future availability. Q15 provides information about the reliability of the service in the form of outages. For the service to be dependable, outages (in particular unscheduled outages) should be kept to a

minimum. Q22 and q23 collect information about the infrastructure and costs of running the service and how these are funded. Costs must be covered for a dependable service available in the long term.

2. *Independence of infrastructure from single providers or funding sources*

Data sources:

- Data source 1: Questions 6, 13e, 22, 23

Explanation:

Information about the modalities through which the service can be accessed from q6 will show whether the service is reliant upon a single mode of access or multiple modes. Q13e, q22 and q23 collect information on the required funding and infrastructure to operate the service and the sources of this funding.

3. *Long-term added value through an established base that new activities can build on*

Data sources:

- Data source 1: Questions 2, 3, 4, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 14, 20, 21
- Data source 2
- Data source 3: Questions 1, 2

Explanation:

Q2, q3, and q4 collect information about what the service offers, and how it compares to competing services. This can demonstrate added value over other services on the market addressing a similar niche. Q7, q8, q9, q10 and q11, along with Data source 2 [3] provide metrics about the use of the service which can demonstrate that the service has an 'established base'. Q14 provides information on how long the service has been operational which also helps demonstrate an 'established base' for those services which have been running for some time. Q20 and q21 along with Data source 3 q1 and q2 collect information on developments made in the past, and future planned developments which demonstrate how value has been added and will continue to be added to a service in the future. It also provides details of some of the new activities which can build on the established service.

4. *Realisation of the benefits of investments made*

Data sources:

- Data source 1: Questions 3, 4, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 13c, 13d, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20
- Data source 2
- Data source 3: Questions 1, 2, 5
- Data source 4

Explanation:

Q3 and 4 provide information on the benefits of the service to its user base and over similar competing services. Q7-11 provide details of the use of the service and the change in use between 2016 and 2017 (in numbers of newly registered users and in submissions). An increase in use is evidence of a benefit of investment as it demonstrates service expansion. Q13 collects information about the outcomes of

training provided for the service, which can demonstrate educational benefit to the users receiving the training. Q16 and q17 assess the penetrance of the service within the community and whether this penetrance is scalable. Significant penetrance, and/or increasing penetrance of the service would be a benefit of investment. Q18 and 19 collect the number of publications citing the service which demonstrate scientific outcomes and benefit from the service. Q20, and Data source 2 q1 and 2 give past developments which have been made to the service to make sure it is up to date and at the cutting edge, development and innovation are tangible benefits of the investment. From Data source 2 KPIs present information on the performance of the service which show the benefits of investment in the service. Data source 3 question 5 collects information on user satisfaction with the survey, high levels of which would show a benefit of investment, satisfied users. Information from Data source 4 shows a benefit to the community and wider society as a whole of outreach activities.

5. *Ability to effectively plan investments and activities*

Data sources:

- Data source 1: Questions 21, 22, 23

Explanation:

Q21-q23 collect information on a plan for the next 2 years and information about the resources required to maintain the service and how those resources are currently funded. This information should demonstrate whether there is a realistic plan in place and what funding/support is required.

6. *A growing body of knowledge shared throughout the community*

Data sources:

- Data source 1: Questions 3, 13, 18, 19, 20, 21
- Data source 4

Explanation:

Q3 asks what benefit is provided by the service to its user base which may include growing knowledge in the community or sharing of knowledge in the community. Q13 collects information about training through which knowledge is shared with the community. Similarly data source 4 collects information on outreach activities through which knowledge is shared with the community. Q18 provides information on the number of publications arising from the service which demonstrates novel research shared with the community and hence a growing body of research (q19 asks how many of these publications have been published in the last year). Q20 and q21 give information on past development of the service and planned future developments of the service which contribute to the growth of knowledge past and present.

7. *Technical evolution that does not lead to legacy issues*

Data sources:

- Data source 1: Questions 20, 21
- Data source 3: Questions 1, 2

Explanation:

Technical evolution is covered by q20 and 21 for both past developments of the service and future planned developments. Data source 3 also collects information on new portals and developments to existing portals.

8. *Embedding of e-Infrastructures in everyday research practice*

Data sources:

- Data source 1: Questions 13, 16, 17, 18, 19

Explanation:

Q13 provides information on training which can be used to teach users how the service can be used in their everyday research. This may be an outcome/goal of a training event. Q16 and q17 assess the penetrance of the service in the structural biology community which provides an indicator of how widespread the knowledge and use of the service is in research practice in the community. Q18 and q19 collect information on the publications acknowledging the service, another indicator of the use of the service in everyday research practice.

9. *Users' needs are met and the costs of uptake are low enough*

Data sources:

- Data source 1: Questions 3, 4, 12, 13, 15, 20, 21
- Data source 3: Question 5

Explanation:

User needs are assessed in q3 and q4 by the service and q12 and q13 gather information on support provided by the service to its users. Q15 collects information on service outages which should be minimal to ensure the user can access the service when they need to. Q20 and q21 detail past and future planned developments which have been made or will be made which may be in order to meet the (changing) needs of users. Data source 5 asks for user feedback on their satisfaction with the service from the satisfaction plugin. Satisfaction of users is a good indicator that their needs are being met.

10. *e-Science 'sells' and an increasing number of users are getting engaged*

Data sources:

- Data source 1: Questions 7b, 7c, 8, 9, 10, 11
- Data source 2
- Data source 4

Explanation:

Information on increasing user engagement in terms use of the service can be assessed from questions 7b, 7c, 8, 9, 10 and 11 and the KPIs in data source 2. Engagement from outreach activities is collected from data source 2.

5. Work plan

1. Distribute the West-Life Sustainability questionnaire to all West-Life service providers and collate the results from the questionnaire into a report (Month 31)
2. Set up an Evaluation Review Panel (ERP) to look at the existing services from each provider and make recommendations to provide sustainability for the structural biology community. The Evaluation Review Panel should be not more than 5 members. Final composition should be approved by Instruct-ERIC Council (as a potential adopter of West-Life services) and the West-Life General Assembly. (Month 31)
3. Develop terms of reference for the ERP to report (Month 32)
4. Present the ERP with the report on the questionnaire results and the terms of reference. (Month 33)
5. Feedback results of ERP to West-Life partners (Month 34)
6. Informed by the ERP, draft the West-Life sustainability plan for deliverable D1.5 (Month 34)
7. Complete D1.5 (Month 36)

6. Interaction with other Work Packages

This milestone ties together work done or in progress in Work Package 1, Work Package 2 and Work Package 5.

7. Conclusion

We presented sustainability aims and recommendations from ESFRI and those specific to e-Infrastructures from the paper of Voss et. al. We then documented in this paper the plans to obtain the relevant information required to complete an assessment of the sustainability of West-Life services. The main source of information for the sustainability assessment will be through the completion of the West-Life sustainability questionnaire (provided in appendix A) for each service, though additional information will be obtained from work delivered by other work packages in particular Work Package 2 and Work Package 5. Each sustainability aim will be assessed with information collected from the data sources detailed. Finally a work plan/timeline was presented to cover the period until the deliverable due date for D1.5 (Month 36). This plan covers the data collection, the review by an external evaluation review panel, and subsequent formulation of a sustainability plan for West-Life informed by their findings.

References

- [1] Hrusak J., Harrison A. Lenoir L., Donzelli M., Carpineti M. & Dell'Arme P. "Long-Term Sustainability of Research Infrastructures" *ESFRI Scripta Volume II*, Dipartimento di Fisica - Università degli Studi di Milano. (2017). ISBN: 978-88-901562-6-7
- [2] Voss, A., Procter, R., Hewitt, W., Asgari-Targhi, M., Daw, M., Baun, C. & Gentzsch, W. "Sustainability of e-Infrastructures (for the Social Sciences)" (2018). https://www.innovationpolicyplatform.org/system/files/Voss_et_al_2007-Sustainability%20of%20e-Infrastructures_0.pdf.

[3] Schaarschmidt, J. "Report on access and usage statistics of the various services".
Zenodo. (2017). doi:10.5281/zenodo.1039053

Glossary

ERP: *Evaluation Review Panel*
ESFRI: *European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures*
LTS: *Long term sustainability*
RI: *Research Infrastructure*

Appendices

Appendix A: West Life Sustainability Questionnaire

About Service

1. Service name:
2. What does the service provide? Please give technical details (approx. 100 words). NB: Information can be copied/adapted from deliverable 5.7
<https://zenodo.org/record/1039054#.WseHd9PwY3g>
3. What benefit does this service give to its user base?
4. What are the competing or alternative services (if any)?
 - a. What demonstrable benefit does this service provide over these competing services?
5. How is the service currently provided? (e.g. Online software provided through webserver) Please give a short description and links to all modalities of access.
6. Is the service available through direct routes other than West-Life; if so which?

Registered Users

7. Is service-specific registration required to use the service? (Yes/No)
If "Yes"
 - a. How many registered users in total?
 - b. How many new registered users in the last year (2017)?
 - c. How many new registered users in the previous year (2016)?

Active Service Usage

8. What is the submission unit recorded (task, job, hour, data (bytes)...)?
9. How many submissions were made in the last year (2017)?
10. How many submissions were made in the previous year (2016)?
11. If submissions are connected to registered users:
 - a. How many users placed submissions in the last year (2017)?
 - b. How many users placed submissions in the previous year (2016)?

Service support

12. Is there support for service users in place (e.g. Manuals, Help guides, telephone help desk, tutorials, use cases, software updates, user forums)? If so give details on:
 - a. The type of support available.
 - b. The frequency of maintenance of support material.
 - c. Metrics on usage of help material (e.g. number of web page views in the past year, number of downloads in the past year, number of emails requesting support in the past year)
13. Is training provided for the service? (Yes/No) If yes give details of:
 - a. Type of training
 - b. Frequency of training
 - c. Outcome of training

- d. Number of participants in training/outreach (per training event)
- e. Resources required to provide this training

Commitment to service

14. How long has the service been operational?
15. Do you log service outages?
 - a. Please provide details of service outages in the last year. (e.g. graphical representation of service provision showing downtime).
 - b. Explain any significant (> 1 day) service outages in this period.
16. What is the penetrance of the service in the structural biology community?
17. Is the service scalable to increase penetrance?

Impact of service

18. What is the total number of publications acknowledging the use of the service?
19. How many of these publications were published within the last year (2017)?

Sustainability of service

20. Give details of past developments (with dates) to the service which have been made to ensure the service provision remains up-to-date with the needs of users and/or scientifically at the cutting-edge.
21. Do you have a plan for future developments of the service over the next 2 years to keep the service relevant and at the cutting-edge (Yes/No).
 - a. If “yes” please give details.
22. What resources (infrastructure and support) are required to continue operation of the service? Please select all that apply and add any resources not included in the list under “other”:
 - Grid/Cloud
 - Local servers
 - Staff [Maintenance/Support/] (please give the number of person months required per year)
 - Other (please specify)
23. For each of the resources listed above, please give an estimated financial cost (per year), and explain how these resources are supported (e.g. funded by X, Staff employed by X).

Appendix B: Work Package 5 Additional Data Collection

1. Did you develop any new web portals? If yes please provide a snapshot and short description.
2. Did you work on any existing portals? E.g.
 - Consolidation of portal machinery
 - Connection to grid / DIRAC4EGI

- Connection to data (e.g. via the VirtualFolder mechanism)
3. Did you recently connect your portal to other (WestLife) portals?
 4. Where are your users coming from?
 5. Have you implemented the satisfaction survey on your results pages?

Appendix C: Work Package 2 Data Collection Outreach Activities

1. Conference Title
2. Presentation Title
3. Organiser
4. Country
5. Audience
6. No. of Participants
7. Represented Countries
8. Date
9. West-Life users training
10. West-Life developer training